

Revitalizing Economics Education through Innovative Teaching Approaches:

The Case of Polya's Problem Solving Instructional Strategy

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effect of Polya's problem solving instructional strategy on students' academic achievement and retention in Economics. The study adopted a quasi-experimental, pretest posttest non-equivalent control group research design. The population of the study comprised all the 31,826 Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Economics students in the 299 public secondary schools in the six Education zones of Imo State. A sample of 192 secondary school (SSII) students that offer Economics was drawn from four public secondary schools in Owerri Education zone 1 of Imo State using the purposive sampling technique. The sample was made up of 98 students in the experimental group and 94 students in the control group. Two research questions and two hypotheses respectively guided the study. Data were collected using a 40-item Multiple Choice Economics Achievement Test (MCEAT). The instrument was subjected to content validation using the test blue print developed by the researcher while the reliability was determined using Kuder Richardson (K-R20) formula to establish the internal consistency of the instrument which yielded a reliability index of 0.78. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results among others showed that Polya's problem solving instructional strategy has increasing positive effects on students' academic achievement and retention in Economics.

Keywords: Polya's problem solving, Instructional strategy, students' academic achievement, retention, Economics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Economics is a dynamic subject which touches our lives daily irrespective of the profession that an individual pursues (Gulati, 2016). More so, all decisions by individuals, businesses and governments are driven by Economic principles. In the same vein, Subhashini (2016) opined that Economics is an evolving social science subject and is significantly related to the framing of economic policies of the nation, and of the world. Similarly, it is a life related discipline and it studies how people and nations are engaged in creating wealth, using it for increasing their welfare, and to manage scarce resources as well as grow wealth overtime. More so, Yusuf (2013) observed that Economics is concerned with human behavior such as how people earn their living and make a choice between alternatives to satisfy their wants.

The popularity of Economics as a school subject grew rapidly following its introduction into the secondary school curriculum. Economics was first taken in the West African School Certificate Examination as a school subject in Nigeria in 1967. Ever since then, Economics has witnessed a phenomenal increase in the number of students' enrolment in external examinations. Apart from English Language and Mathematics which are compulsory subjects, the highest entry

figures (over 70% of the total candidature) were recorded in Economics. Despite the high enrolment of students in external examinations in Economics not much could be said as regard to students' academic achievement (Nneji, 2013).

Academic achievement refers to an expression used to represent students' scholastic standing (Glawala, 2016). Similarly, Ishaku (2015) saw achievement as a test for the measurement and accomplishment of skills in various field of academic performance as what an individual can obtain within a specific criteria domain. He further described academic achievement as a systematic and purposeful quantification of learning outcome. Thus, it is therefore, not out of place to describe academic achievement as the gain in knowledge of students as a result of taking part in a learning activity or programme. Academic achievement of students represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university (Steinmayr, Meibner, Weidinger & Wirthwein, 2015). Academic achievement, according to Ajobeje in Glawala et al (2016), refers to an expression used to represent students scholastic standing while Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidile, (2016) saw academic achievement as the outcome of students' effort in examinations.

The achievement of students in Economics at Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) over the years has not been encouraging. This is evidenced in the West African Examination Council Chief Examiners Reports of various years which shows that between 35% and 50% of the candidates passed Economics at credit level (grades A1-C6) in 2018. Furthermore, statistics of results in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination for school candidates in 2019 to 2021 in Nigeria showed that between 42% and 59% of the candidates passed Economics at credit level (grades A1-C6). The Chief Examiners also reported that a good number of candidates have poor knowledge of drawing graphs and simple calculations and could not compute values from graph. They also showed great deficiency in the application of graphical representations to economic analysis (WAEC Chief Examiners Reports May/June, 2019, Nov/Dec, 2021). Poor academic achievement in Economics as buttressed above could be due to poor retention of what was taught.

Retention is the ability to keep or retain what is learnt and be able to recall it when it is required (Safo, Ezenwa & Wushishi, 2013). Hornby (2013) defined retention as the fact of keeping something in one's memory. Retention is the ability to possess, use or keep information and ability to reproduce past experiences or previously familiar materials (Okoro, 2013). Retention according to Ngwoke (2010) is the process by which a child stores information in his memory for use at a later period. Retention occurs when facts or experiences are stored in the long term memory. A student may be able to memorize facts in the short term, but may not retain those facts over the long term memory. In the context of this study retention is the ability to recall or remember what has been taught after a given time as a measure of students' progress. Knowledge retention of Economics concepts could lead to high academic achievement in the subject. Some studies found that retention of learning were more with one method of teaching than the other (Klegeris and Hurren, 2011; Okoro, 2013 and Hoidn and Karkkainen, 2014) while others found that there was no significant difference in students' knowledge retention using different methods of teaching except after a long time (Wynn, Mosholder, and Larsen, 2014).

Poor academic achievement and retention of knowledge of Economics taught seem to depend or be caused by inadequate knowledge and use of teaching methods. Research evidences have consistently indicated teaching method as a major factor determining the achievement and retention of students in Economics. It has also been reported that learning and understanding of school subjects have been frustrated by the clumsy methods and instructional materials used (Eze, et al, 2016). To support this assertion, Inuwa and Yusof (2012) noted that poor academic achievement in public examination is traceable to poor teaching methodology. Similarly, Emaikwu in Dangpe (2015) submitted that the fall in standard of achievement at post primary level is incontrovertibly attributable to pedagogical approaches adopted by teachers in schools. The resultant effect is the low achievement and low retention level in students' outcome both in internal and external examinations. On problems of retention, Nneji (2013) asserted that failure to provide enough applications to real life activity and social usage cum poor teaching techniques are strong limiting factors to students' retention in Economics.

The senior secondary Economics was designed as learner centred and activity oriented curriculum. However, the practice by teachers in the traditional instructional strategy does not allow active participation of students in the learning process. The result as reported by Akusoba and Okeke (2009) is that students are passive in the classroom and thus continue to record low achievements in Economics. This study was therefore, an attempt to fill that gap especially in topics involving mathematical calculations and graphical analysis where the problem of teaching and learning difficulty is said to occur most in Economics. Hence this study on the effect of Polya's problem solving instructional strategy on students' academic achievement and retention in Economics.

Polya's problem solving instructional strategy was named after its proponent, George Polya. Polya identified four basic principles of problem solving. He outlined the sequence of problem solving strategy as follows: understanding the problem, devising a plan to solve the problem, carrying out the plan, and looking back. Meanwhile, understanding the problem begins with the identification of what the problem is asking for. For this purpose, it is important to recognize all available data in the problem. Polya taught teachers how to prompt students with appropriate questions, depending on the situation such as: what are you asked to find or show? Can you restate the problem in your own words? Can you think of a picture or a diagram that might help you understand the problem? and so on.

Devising a plan entails that there are many ways to solve problems. The skill at choosing an appropriate strategy is best learned by solving many problems. A partial list of strategies to solve problems by Polya includes drawing a picture/diagram, using a formula, using a model, solving an equation, and so on. In general, all that is needed in carrying out the plan is care and patience, given that one has the necessary skills. Persist with the plan that has been chosen. If it continues not to work, discard it and choose another. Looking back involves taking the time to reflect, review and look back at what has been done, what worked, and what didn't. Doing this will enable one to predict what strategy to use to solve future problems. A solved problem does not mean that the process of problem solving has ended. Here, we determine whether the result obtained is reasonable by looking back or checking through the earlier stages.

The advantages of Polya's problem-solving strategy are that it helps in the development of reflective thinking, and develops in the students the skill of organizing information in a

logical manner. Reflection makes learners to understand new idea, relate it to their previous knowledge, adapt it to achieve their own purpose, and translate their ideas into action. Thus, reflection develops in the students, critical thinking and creativity. The study therefore was to investigate the effect of Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on secondary school students' academic achievement and retention in Economics.

2. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on secondary school students' academic achievement and retention in Economics. Specifically, the study determined the effect of:

1. Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in Economics.
2. Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on student's retention in Economics.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in Economics?
2. What is the effect of Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy on students' retention in Economics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁** Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy has no significant effect on students' academic achievement in Economics.
- H₀₂** Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy has no significant effect on students' retention in Economics.

3. METHODS

The researcher adopted the quasi - experimental study with non-randomized, non-equivalent pre-test and posttest control group design. The design was suitable for the study because intact classes were used and were randomly assigned to both treatment and control groups. The quasi-experimental design was used because the true randomization of the subject was impossible since intact classes were used. Variables in the study are: independent variables (Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy and lecture method), and dependent variables (students' academic achievement and retention in Economics).

The population of the study comprised all the 31826 Senior Secondary School II (SS2) Economics students in the 299 public secondary schools in the six education zones of Imo State. They were comprised 15,746 male and 16,080 female students. (Secondary Education Management Board, Imo State, 2020/2021). The sample of the study consisted of 192 SS2 Economics students comprising 98 in the experimental group and 94 in the control group in four public secondary schools in Owerri education zone I. A three-stage sampling was used. In the first stage, purposive sampling was used to select Owerri Education zone 1 from the six education zones in the state. In the second stage, purposive sampling technique was used to select four schools for the study. Where more than one intact class existed in each of the four sampled schools, an intact class was selected for the study. Finally, simple random sampling by balloting without replacement was used to assign the four sampled schools into groups.

The groups were assigned as follows: Government Secondary School, Owerri and Girls' Secondary School, Akwakuma for experimental group and Emmanuel College, Owerri and Imo Girls' Secondary School, Owerri for control group. The sampled schools were purposively selected based on the following criteria: have qualified and experienced Economics teachers, are currently presenting candidates for senior secondary school certificate examination in Economics for the past 10 years, have good number of students offering Economics, are government owned, and must have more than one stream of SS II classes offering Economics. The instrument used for data collection was a Multiple-Choice Economics Achievement Test (MCEAT). This instrument was developed by the researcher and it was made up of 48 multiple choice questions with options A-D. The MCEAT was made up of two parts, part A contains the personal data of the respondent while part B contains the multiple-choice items responded to by the subjects involved in the study. The items were drawn using a table of specification to ensure adequate coverage of the contents/topics as well as maintain even spread across the different levels of the cognitive domain.

Multiple Choice Economics Achievement Test (MCEAT) was face validated by three experts. It was face validated by one expert in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Science Education and the other from the Department of Science Education, (Economics Education Unit) both from Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. Also, the use of a head teacher of Economics from Secondary Commercial School, Obiangwu, Ngor Okpala in Imo State. To achieve this, validators were given copies of the purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses, table of specification, 48-item Multiple Choice Economics Achievement Test and marking scheme. The instrument was scrutinized for relevance, clarity and content coverage based on the topics selected for the study. A total of 48 multiple-choice items were developed by the researcher and was subjected to item analysis. After, the items were first subjected to content validation using test blue print. The use of item analysis was to ensure the adequacy of each item of the instrument in terms of its difficulty, discrimination and distracter index. This resulted in the scaling down of the items to 40 questions

The reliability of the instrument, MCEAT was trial tested using 20 (SS3) Economics students of Ibeku High School, Umuahia in Abia State, who were not part of the present study. The Kuder-Richardson's formula 20 ($K - R_{20}$) was employed in the determination of the internal consistency of the instrument since the items of the instrument used were dichotomously or objectively scored. This was established using Kuder-Richardson's formula 20 ($K - R_{20}$) statistic which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78. This reliability coefficient was considered adequate for the level of the internal consistency of the instrument.

At the beginning of the experiment, Multiple-Choice Economics Achievement Test (MCEAT 1) was administered to both the experimental and control groups as pretest. This was conducted by the regular Economics class teacher who were trained by the researcher and used as researcher assistants. At the end of the test, scores obtained by the students were recorded and kept. More so, at the end of the treatment, MCEAT 11 which was the same test as MCEAT 1 but reshuffled and restructured was administered to the two groups as posttest. The scores obtained were marked, recorded and kept. Furthermore, a third test, MCEAT III, which was the same test as MCEAT II but reshuffled and restructured, was administered to the two groups after two weeks to test the students' retention. All scores obtained by both groups were analyzed to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses formulated for the study.

3.1 Experimental Procedure

Two instructional packages were developed by the researcher. The first package was based on the Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy, and the second was based on the conventional instructional method. The researcher trained the research assistants (regular Economics teachers) in the selected schools for one week. At the beginning of the experiment the research subjects in both treatment and control groups were given pretest (MCEAT I) by respective trained research assistants. At the end of the test, the scores were recorded and kept. After the pretest, the research assistants carried out the treatment in their respective schools ensuring compliance with the instructional guide developed by the researcher. The experiment lasted for four weeks based on the regular school timetable. The posttest, (MCEAT II) / (pretest reshuffled) were administered to the subjects at the end of the experimental period. The scores were recorded and kept. Two weeks later, the post posttest (MCEAT III), which was the posttest reshuffled and paper colour changed, was re-administered to ascertain the retention ability of the subjects in both groups. All scores obtained by both groups were analyzed to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses formulated for the study.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA was used because the pretest scores were used as covariates to the post test scores to partial out the initial difference between the groups. The decision rule for the rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses was, if the P-value is equal to or greater than the alpha value, we accept null hypothesis but if P- value is less than the 0.05 alpha value, we reject the null hypothesis.

4. RESULTS

The results from the data analysis done were presented in the tables below:

Research Question 1:

What is the effect of Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy on students’ achievement?

The data for answering research question 1 were analyzed with mean and standard deviation and results presented in table 6.1

Table 1. Pretest and posttest mean scores of students taught Economics using Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy and Lecture method.

Group	Pretest			Post test		Mean Scores	Gain
	N	X	SD	X	SD		
Polya’s problem solving instructional strategy	98	48.86	7.30	57.84	7.44	8.98	
Conventional instructional strategy	94	47.82	7.11	50.61	6.97	2.79	
Effect						6.19	

Data in Table 1 show that the students taught with Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy had a Pretest mean of 48.86 with standard deviation of 7.30 and a Posttest mean of 57.84 with standard deviation of 7.44, while conventional instructional strategy had a Pre-test

mean of 47.82 with standard deviation of 7.11 and a posttest mean score of 50.61 with the standard deviation of 6.97. The result also shows that Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy had a mean gain of 8.98 while those of the lecture method group had a mean gain of 2.79. The table showed that Polya’s problem solving instructional strategy had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.19 on the students’ academic achievements in Economics. This showed that students taught Economics using Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy had higher mean achievements than those taught using the lecture method.

A corresponding hypothesis that addressed the above research question is:

Hypothesis 1:

Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy has no significant effect on students’ academic achievement in Economics. The data for testing hypothesis 1 were analyzed with ANCOVA and the results presented in Table 2

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Achievement Scores of Students taught Economics using Polya’s problem-solving Instructional Strategy and Lecture Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	40862.085 ^a	2	20431.043	200.304	.000
Intercept	5174.180	1	5174.180	50.727	.000
Pretest Group	4547.451	1	4547.45	44.582	.000
	2163.153	1	2163.153	21.207	.000
Error	3658.544	98	43.67		*
Total	205493.000	102			
Corrected Total	24489.739	101			

Table 2 shows that a significant P-value of .000 was obtained. Since the probability value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis stated is rejected. Therefore, Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy has statistical significant effect on students’ academic achievements in Economics. This implied that the use of Polya’s problem-solving instructional strategy in teaching Economics resulted in higher mean achievement scores of students.

Research Question 2:

What is the effect of Polya’s problem –solving instructional strategy on students’ retention in Economics?

The data for answering research question 2 were analyzed with mean and standard deviation and results presented in table 3

Table 3: Posttest and Retention mean scores of students taught Economics using Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy and lecture method.

Group	Posttest			Retention		Retention mean gain
	N	X	SD	X	SD	
Polya's problem-solving Instructional Strategy	98	34.48	4.00	50.44	6.85	15.96
Conventional instructional strategy	94	25.06	4.27	37.66	5.73	12.60
Effect						3.36

Table 3 reveals that students taught Economics using Polys's problem-solving instructional strategy had a mean retention gain of 15.96 while those in the conventional method had mean retention gain of 12.60. The table further revealed that Polya's problem – solving instructional strategy had an increasing positive effect of 3.36 on students' retention in Economics.

A corresponding hypothesis that addressed the above research question is:

Hypothesis 2:

Polya's Problem-solving instructional strategy has no significant effect on s retention in Economics.

The data for testing hypothesis 2 were analyzed with ANCOVA and the results presented in table 4

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Retention Scores of Students taught Economics using Polya's Problem-solving Instructional Strategy and Lecture Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	8349.498 ^a	3	2783.166	182.527	.000
Intercept	62.234	1	62.234	4.0815	.000
Posttest	1712.485	1	1712.485	112.309	.000
Gender	1.294	1	1.294	.0849	.581
Method	2188.223	2	1094.112	71.75	.000
Error	1494.324	98	15.248		
Total	159988.000	102			
Corrected Total	9843.822	101			

The data in table 6.4 reveal a probability –value of .000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis stated was rejected. Therefore, Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy has significant effect on students' retention in Economics. In other words, students exposed to Polya's problem–solving instructional strategy had higher retention in Economics.

4.1 Discussion of the Findings

The discussion of findings was carried out sequentially based on the research questions and hypothesis that guided the study.

The findings of the study revealed that students taught Economics using Polya's problem-

solving instructional strategy achieved more compared to group taught using conventional method. A further test indicated that there is statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores of senior secondary students taught Economics using Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy compared to group taught using conventional method (Control group). This result agrees with Olaniyan et al (2015) and Nneji (2013) who found out in their separate studies that students who were exposed to Polya's problem-solving strategy performed better than students exposed to conventional method in Physics and Mathematics respectively. Similarly, the researcher in his study found out that students exposed to Polya's problem-solving strategy performed better than students exposed to conventional method in Economics. Also, the finding is in line with Mahmud, et al (2016), Riasat, et al (2010), Adewumi and Akinnodi (2016) who in their separate studies found that students taught by problem-solving strategy performed better than those taught by conventional lecture method in Biology and Mathematics respectively. Moreso, the result further authenticates the findings of Okafor (2019) and that of Abbas and Habu (2014) whose separate reports revealed that students taught with Polya's problem-solving technique performed better than those taught with conventional technique. The result from the study indicated that Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy had an increasing positive effect on students' retention in Economics. This means that students taught Economics using Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy had higher mean retention than those taught using conventional method. The result further showed that Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy had significant effect on students' retention in Economics. The above result corroborated with those of Mahmud, et al (2016) and Nneji (2013) who in their separate studies discovered that students taught Biology and Mathematics respectively using Polya's problem solving instructional strategy had higher mean retention than others taught using the conventional method. The result further agrees with the famous dictum of Confucius around 45 BC which stated: "Tell me, and I will forget. Show me, and I may remember. Involve me, and I will understand.

5. CONCLUSION

Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy has an increasing significant effect on the students' academic achievement and retention in Economics. The effectiveness of Polya learning strategy on students' achievement in Economics over the conventional teaching method could be due to the fact that students are allowed to discover for themselves functional and relevant information that lead to expected solution under the guidance of the teacher. In other words, the approach guides and stimulates the learner into discovering the solutions to certain problems by themselves.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusion, the following recommendations were outlined.

1. Teachers should endeavour to use Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy to teach Economics at senior secondary schools.
2. Government should organize regular workshops and seminars for teachers on effective use of Polya's problem-solving instructional strategy to teach Economics at senior secondary schools.
3. School curriculum should be overhauled to accommodate problem –solving and activity-oriented teaching strategies.
4. Students should develop a proper attitude towards problem solving with a view to improving their performance in Economics as well as making them functional to themselves and the society at large.

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